

Principles of the scholarly commons

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Principles

P1. The scholarly commons is an agreement among knowledge producers and users.

This means that:

- The commons is developed by its members through their practice
- There is global commitment and participation in the commons' long-term viability and preservation

P2. Research and knowledge should be freely available to all who wish to use or reuse it.

This means that:

- The commons is open by default
- Scholarly objects and content in the commons is FAIR: findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable by humans and machines

P3. Participation in the production and use of knowledge should be open to all who wish to participate.

This means that:

- The commons welcomes and encourages participants of all backgrounds
- The commons is open to all participants who accept its principles

Rules

In order to effect these principles, participants in the commons agree that:

R1: The rewards for participating in the commons are access, opportunity and attribution

This means that:

- Provenance of objects in the commons should be transparent and persistent
- The commons has no intrinsic hierarchies, rankings, or reward systems

R2: The commons is agnostic regarding form and technology

This means that:

- The commons exists independently of technology, funding, and business models that support and enable it

- The commons accepts all contributed objects that adhere to its guidelines on an equal basis regardless of form, genre or approaches

R3: (Use of) external systems or technology, including reward systems, must not harm the commons.

This means that:

- The form research is disseminated in is determined by the needs of the research itself
- All activities and outputs that take place in in the commons remain in the commons